

EXPERIMENTS ON THE SYNTHESSES OF FURANO COMPOUNDS.
PART I. A NOVEL ROUTE TO β -BRAZANS*

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An unambiguous synthesis of Kostacecki's 3 : 8 : 9-trimethoxy- β -brazan has been achieved by the cyclodehydration of 6-methoxy-3-(3 : 4-dimethoxybenzyl)-2-formylcoumarone obtained by the Gattermann reaction on 6-methoxy-3-(3 : 4-dimethoxybenzyl)-coumarone which has been synthesised in two different ways. The Hoesch reaction on the latter is shown to give 2-acyl derivative. The cyclisations of a few 2-acyl-3-benzylcoumarones have been studied.

β -Brazan (I) (phenylene- $\beta\beta$ -naphthylene oxide) is known to accompany 1 : 2-benzonaphthacene in the coal-tar distillate (Fieser, "Chemistry of natural products related to phenanthrene", Reinhold Publishing Corp., 1937, p. 20). An important derivative of this substance is 3 : 8 : 9-trimethoxy- β -brazan (IV, R-H) obtained from the natural product brazilin (a pyrane compound). By heating O-trimethylbrazilone (II) with hydriodic acid for a long period, Kostanecki and Lloyd (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 2198) obtained 3 : 8 : 9-trihydroxy- β -brazan which gave the trimethyl ether (IV, R-H) (m. p. 244-46") on methylation. In this reaction, the diketone (II) undergoes a remarkable rearrangement to the coumarone derivative (III)

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

which then cyclises to 3 : 6 : 8 : 9-tetrahydroxy- β -brazan (IV, R-OH and OH in place of OMe). The latter is reduced by a further action of hydriodic acid to 3 : 8 : 9-trihydroxy- β -brazan the constitution of which has been confirmed by converting the hydroxybrazan into β -brazan (I) with the aid of zinc dust (cf. Perkin and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 386). Although a number of syntheses of β -brazan are known (Kostanecki and Lampe, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 2373 ; Mosettig and Robinson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 1149 ; Orchin and Reggel, *ibid.*, 1948, 70, 1245 ; cf. Ebel, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1929, 12, 3), the methods are by no means

*A preliminary account of a part of the work appeared in *Experientia*, 1951, 7, 374.

general and universally applicable. The present communication deals with an unambiguous and general method for the synthesis of 3 : 8 : 9-trimethoxy- β -brazan and some of its derivatives.

The keto-nitrile (V) of Pfeiffer *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1930, 63, 1304), obtained by the condensation of ethyl *m*-methoxyphenoxyacetate with homoveratronic nitrile, gives the amide (VI) with fuming hydrochloric acid in acetic acid at the room temperature (15°-18°). At the higher temperature (30°), the sole crystalline product, however, was the cyclised amide (VII). This on prolonged boiling with 10% hydrochloric acid afforded 6-methoxy-3-(3 : 4-dimethoxybenzyl)coumarone (VIII, R-H) (isolated through the picrate) with the loss of the amide group by hydrolysis and decarboxylation. The constitution of this compound was confirmed by obtaining it from 5-methoxy-2-(3 : 4-dimethoxyphenylacetyl)phenoxyacetic acid (IX) (Bentley and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1355) by the action of sodium acetate and hot

(V)

(VI)

(VII)

(VIII)

(IX)

(X)

acetic anhydride. On Gattermann synthesis with hydrogen cyanide and zinc chloride, (VIII, R-H) furnished the aldehyde (VIII, R-CHO) the orientation of which was established by oxidising it with potassium permanganate in acetone to the known acid (VIII, R-CO₂H) obtained by Bentley and Robinson (*loc. cit.*) by the cyclisation of the phenoxyacetic acid (IX) with sodium ethoxide. The aldehyde (VIII, R-CHO) underwent quantitative Bergmann cyclisation* on short

* This type of cyclisation was first observed by Bergmann (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1939, 4, 1) who obtained anthracene as one of the products of hydrolysis of the acetal of *o*-benzylbenzaldehyde.

treatment with glacial phosphoric acid at 100° giving the β -brazan (IV, R-H) (m. p. 244-46°). Although the synthetic product was not compared with that from the natural sources, the correctness of the synthesis was confirmed by typical reactions (cf. *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 2198) and by oxidising it with chromic acid to the known trimethoxybrazanquinone (X) (m. p. 261-62°), obtained by Kostanecki and Lloyd in a different way (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 2200).

The Hoesch reaction with the coumarones does not appear to have been studied in detail. Karrer *et al.* (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1919, 2, 454; 1920, 3, 541; 1921, 4, 718) had obtained 5-acyl or aroyl derivatives by the Hoesch reaction with 6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarone*. In the present case, however, the coumarone (VIII, R-H) gave with acetonitrile and zinc chloride the 2-aceto compound (VIII, R-COMe). The orientation of this compound was established by preparing it in the following way :

The oxime of the aldehyde (VIII, R-CHO) on dehydration with acetic anhydride furnished the nitrile (VIII, R-CN) which with methylmagnesium iodide gave the ketone (VIII, R-COMe) identical with the Hoesch condensation product. Attempts to obtain this ketone by the action of diazomethane on the aldehyde (VIII, R-CHO) were unsuccessful; while intractable tar was obtained by the action of acetic anhydride and stannic chloride on (VIII, R=H) (cf. Smith's method of acylation of coumarones, *Chem. Abs.*, 1938, 32, 2938). An attempt to cyclise the nitrile by internal Hoesch reaction so as to obtain (XI) was also unsuccessful.

The syntheses of 2-propionyl, 2-*n*-butyryl, 2-*isobutyryl* derivatives of the coumarone were similarly done by the action of appropriate Grignard's reagent on the nitrile (VIII, R=CN).

A purely qualitative study on the case of cyclisation of the various acyl derivatives (VIII, R-CHO or COMe etc.) showed that while the aldehyde (VIII, R-CHO) cyclised with glacial phosphoric acid at 100° during 10 minutes, the acetyl compound (VIII, R-COMe) did so during one and half hours and the propionyl compound (VIII, R-COEt) cyclised only at a higher temperature (180°-185°). The *n*-butyryl compound (VIII, R-COPr) and the *isobutyryl* compound [VIII, R-COCH(CH₃)₂] did not cyclise even at higher temperatures, instead these showed signs of decomposition. The ease of cyclisation is thus dependent on the nature of groups attached to the carbonyl group, the relative order being $\text{H} > \text{CH}_3 > \text{C}_2\text{H}_5 > \begin{matrix} \text{C}_3\text{H}_7 \text{ (}n\text{)} \\ \text{C}_3\text{H}_7 \text{ (}iso\text{)} \end{matrix}$ which is in the increasing order of +I effect. The result falls in line with the observations by Berliner (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 533) who found a similar order in the rate constants in the cyclisations of various

* Robertson *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2057) have proved that Karrer's were really 2-acyl coumarone.

alkyl ketones having similar structural features. Berliner found an explanation for the decrease in the rate of cyclisation with increasing length of the alkyl chain in terms of the increasing electron releasing character of the alkyl group. The electron

release increases the electron density of the positively charged central carbon atom of the conjugate acid (XII) (which is the intermediate in the process of cyclisation) decreasing the effective positive character and therefore a decrease in the rate results.

It is proposed to extend this synthesis of β -brazans to other cases.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

(All m.p.'s are uncor.)

Keto-nitrile (V) was prepared according to Pfeiffer *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) by the condensation of ethyl *m*-methoxyphenoxyacetate and homoveratronic nitrile in the presence of alcoholic sodium ethoxide. The product was freed from oily impurities by pressing over a porous pot and crystallised from acetic acid, as hard prisms, m. p. 92-94° (lit. m. p., 95°). (Found : C, 67.0 ; H, 5.8. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{19}O_5N$: C, 66.8 ; H, 5.6 per cent).

6-*Methoxy-3-[\alpha-(3:4-dimethoxyphenylacetamido)]coumarone* (VII).—A solution of the foregoing keto-nitrile (24.0g.) in acetic acid (350 c.c.) was treated at the room temperature with fuming hydrochloric acid (250 c. c., sat. at 0°). The mixture was well corked and maintained at 30° for 24 hours. The brown solution was added to a large volume of water and the precipitate (24 g.) collected after 24 hours, dried and crystallised from alcohol. The coumarone was obtained in colorless, flat needles (11.5 g.), m. p. 162°. (Found : C, 67.1 ; H, 5.8. $C_{19}H_{19}O_5N$ requires C, 66.8 ; H, 5.6 per cent). The compound gives no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

6-*Methoxy-3-(3:4-dimethoxybenzyl)coumarone* (VIII, R-H). *Method (a)*.—The above amide (5.0 g.) was boiled under reflux with hydrochloric acid (10% 140 c.c.) for 6 hours when the solid gradually became completely oily. The mixture was cooled, extracted with ether (2×40 c.c.) and the product treated with a strong solution of alcoholic picric acid. The picrate of the coumarone (VIII, R-H) (5.4 g.) was collected and crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine, orange needles, m. p. 102°. (Found : N, 7.6. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4 \cdot C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 8.0 per cent)•

It was obtained quantitatively from the picrate by washing an ethereal suspension of the picrate several times with dilute sodium hydroxide. On removal of ether, an oil was obtained which quickly solidified. The product crystallised from methanol in colorless needles, m. p. 61-62°. (Found : C, 72.2, 72.4 ; H, 6.6, 6.2. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 72.5 ; H, 6.4 per cent). It gives no colour reaction with ferric chloride. It gives a red coloration with sulphuric acid. The compound is easily soluble in all organic solvents.

Method (b). From 5-Methoxy-2-(3 : 4-dimethoxyphenylacetyl)phenoxyacetic Acid (IX) (cf. J. Chem. Soc., 1950, 1355).—The above mentioned acid was conveniently prepared as follows: A mixture of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl-3' : 4'-dimethoxybenzyl ketone (5 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (35 c. c.), potassium carbonate (15 g.) and acetone (50 c. c.) was heated under reflux for 6 hours. On removal of acetone, ethyl 5-methoxy-2-(3 : 4-dimethoxyphenylacetyl)phenoxyacetate was obtained as a non-crystallisable gum. This ester was hydrolysed by boiling under reflux for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour with a solution of potassium hydroxide (6.0 g.) in alcohol (30 c. c.) containing water (10 c. c.). After removing alcohol in vacuum, the residue was diluted with water (80 c. c.) and 5-methoxy-2-(3 : 4-dimethoxyphenylacetyl)phenoxyacetic acid precipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid. Crystallised from glacial acetic acid, it was obtained in colorless needles (2.3 g.), m. p. 143°. (Found : C, 63.0 ; H, 5.7. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{20}O_7$: C, 63.3 ; H, 5.6 per cent).

A mixture of this phenoxy-acid (IX, 1.0g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (1.0 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 c. c.) was heated at 160° (oil-bath) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and then poured into water. The gummy material was isolated by extraction with ether and then treated with alcoholic picric acid when the picrate (0.8g.) of (VIII, R-H) was obtained crystallising from alcohol in orange needles, m. p. and mixed m. p. 102°.

6-Methoxy-3-(3 : 4-dimethoxybenzyl)-2-formylcoumarone (VIII, R-CHO).—A solution of the coumarone (VIII, R-H) (1.0g.) and anhydrous hydrogen cyanide (1.5 c. c.) in ether (50 c. c.) containing zinc chloride (0.4g.) was saturated with hydrogen chloride at 0°. The crystalline aldimine hydrochloride appeared in course of $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. Next day, the greenish product was washed twice with dry ether, treated with water and heated on the water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The oily material that had first appeared was quickly replaced by a crystalline mass which was collected (1.0 g.) and obtained from alcohol in yellowish clusters of hexagonal plates, m.p. 137°. (Found : C, 69.7 ; H, 5.5. $C_{19}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 69.9 ; H, 5.5 per cent). On being diluted with water the red solution of this compound in sulphuric acid became green and then blue.

The 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone separated from ethyl acetate in orange-red microcrystalline powder, m. p. 246-48°. (Found : N, 10.9. $C_{25}H_{22}O_9N_4$ requires N, 11.7 per cent).

The semicarbazone crystallised from alcohol in yellowish plates, m. p. 166-67°. (Found : N, 10.3. $C_{20}H_{21}O_5N_3$ requires N, 11.0 per cent). With sulphuric acid

the compound gives a yellow coloration; on addition of water this turns green and then a red precipitate is obtained. Addition of alkali destroys this red colour which may be regenerated on acidification.

The *oxime* was prepared by heating the aldehyde (VIII, R=CHO) (4.0 g.) in pyridine (10 c. c.) with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (3 g.) on the water-bath for 2 hours. It crystallised from aqueous alcohol in colorless needles, m. p. 145-45.5°, yield 3.9 g. (Found: N, 3.9. $C_{19}H_{19}O_5N$ requires N, 4.1 per cent).

6-Methoxy-3-(3:4-dimethoxybenzyl)coumarilic Acid (VIII, R=CO₂H).—A solution of KMnO₄ (1.0 g.) in water (20 c. c.) was gradually added to the above-mentioned aldehyde (0.41 g.) in acetone (20 c. c.) at 50° during 1 hour. The mixture was cooled, cleaned by passing sulphur dioxide into the solution and then diluted with water (100 c. c.). The colorless crystalline precipitate (0.28 g.) of the coumarilic acid was collected and crystallised from acetic acid in colorless, slender needles, m. p. 196° (lit., 196.5°). (Found: C, 66.8; H, 5.4. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{19}O_6$: C, 66.6; H, 5.3 per cent). With a view to preparing the 6-nitro derivative of this compound (nitration in the veratrole nucleus), experiments on nitration were undertaken when an unidentified product was obtained as follows: A solution of the coumarilic acid (0.4 g.) was gradually treated at the room temperature with a mixture of nitric acid (0.3 c. c.), acetic acid (0.2 c. c.) and sulphuric acid (0.1 c. c.). The solution at once turned yellow and gradually a yellow crystalline solid appeared. The product was collected after 1½ hours and crystallised from acetic acid and obtained in yellow flakes, m. p. 182-84°. (Found: C, 54.8; H, 5.1%). The product is insoluble in alkali.

*3:8:9-Trimethoxy-β-braza*n (IV, R=H).—*6-Methoxy-3-(3:4-dimethoxybenzyl)-2-formylcoumarone* (1.0 g.) was suspended in glacial phosphoric acid (25 c. c.) and the mixture maintained at 100° for about 10 minutes. At first a greenish jelly was obtained which afterwards turned greyish white. The product was heated with water (100 c. c.) for a few minutes on the water-bath and the colorless product collected and washed thoroughly with water and alcohol. The compound crystallised from benzene in colorless, thick plates, m. p. 244-46° (Kostanecki, m. p. 244-46°), yield 0.9 g. (Found: C, 73.9; H, 5.2. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{16}O_4$: C, 74.0; H, 5.2 per cent). The compound is sparingly soluble in acetic acid and alcohol. With sulphuric acid the coloration is at first deep blue and then violet and finally turns green on keeping (in agreement with Kostanecki).

*Trimethoxy-β-braza*nquinone (X) (cf. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 1150).—A solution of the above braza)n (0.4 g.) in acetic acid (12 c. c.) was treated gradually at the boiling point with a solution of chromic acid (1.0 g.) in a mixture of acetic acid (8 c. c.) and water (1 c. c.). After boiling for 10 minutes, the solution was cooled and water added to precipitate the quinone. The crude product (0.2 g.) was collected and trimethoxy-β-braza)nquinone was obtained from acetic acid in fine, orange-red needles, m. p. 260-62°. The product may be further

purified and obtained in bright, orange-red, pointed needles, m. p. 261-62° by sublimation at 200° in vacuum (1 mm.), yield 0.05 g. (Found : C, 67.2 ; H, 4.3. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{14}O_6$: C, 67.5 ; H, 4.1 per cent). The compound is reduced by warm alkaline sodium hydrosulphite to a yellow solution. On addition of sulphuric acid, the compound gives a brownish solution having a violet tinge and on keeping the solution turns green.

6-Methoxy-3-(3 : 4-dimethoxybenzyl)-2-acetocoumarone (VIII, R-COMe).—A solution of the coumarone (VIII, R-H) (0.5 g.) in ether (30 c. c.) containing zinc chloride (0.3 g.) was treated with acetonitrile (1 c. c.) and saturated at 0° with dry hydrogen chloride. The solution was allowed to stay in the refrigerator and after 6 days the green solid was washed with dry ether and then heated with water (50 c. c.) on the water-bath. The crystalline mass (0.15 g.) of the product separated from alcohol in colorless, pointed plates, m. p. 156-57°. (Found : C, 70.3 ; H, 6.1. $C_{20}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 70.6 ; H, 5.9 per cent). The yield of the product does not improve if anhydrous aluminium chloride be used along with zinc chloride as a catalyst. The red solution of the compound in sulphuric acid turns gradually green and then finally blue.

The 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from nitrobenzene-alcohol in deep orange-red plates, m. p. 227°. (Found : N, 10.6. $C_{26}H_{24}O_8N_4$ requires N, 10.8 per cent).

The oxime (prepared in pyridine) crystallised from methanol in colorless needles, m. p. 131-32°. (Found : N, 3.6. $C_{20}H_{21}O_5N$ requires N, 4.0 per cent).

6-Methoxy-3-(3 : 4-dimethoxybenzyl)-2-cyanocoumarone (VIII, R-CN).—A solution of the oxime of (VIII, R-CHO, mentioned above) (4.0 g.) in acetic anhydride (8 c. c.) was heated under reflux for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and then poured into water. The gummy solid was crystallised from alcohol and the compound was obtained in cream-colored flat needles, m. p. 130-31°, yield 2.4 g. (Found : C, 69.8, 69.9 ; H, 5.3, 5.4. $C_{19}H_{17}O_4N$ requires C, 70.0 ; H, 5.2 per cent). If the period of heating be shortened (2-3 mins.), a mixture of this cyano compound and the acetyl derivative of the oxime of (VIII, R-CHO) is obtained which may be separated by fractional crystallisation from alcohol. The latter, which is more soluble, separates in colorless prisms, m. p. 118°. (Found : N, 3.6. $C_{21}H_{21}O_6N$ requires N, 3.7 per cent). The compound is easily hydrolysed by acids to the aldehyde (VIII, R-CHO) and may be converted into the nitrile (VIII, R-CN) on further treatment with acetic anhydride.

Alternative Preparation of 6-Methoxy-3-(3 : 4-dimethoxybenzyl)-2-acetocoumarone.—A solution of the above nitrile (0.25 g.) in dry benzene (2 c. c.) was added dropwise in the cold to an excess of methylmagnesium iodide from methyl iodide (0.9 g.) and magnesium (0.1 g.) in ether (15 c. c.). The mixture was refluxed for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours and left overnight. Next day, the mixture was carefully decomposed with ice-cold hydrochloric acid and the aqueous layer was quickly withdrawn. This deposited the ketone (VIII, R-COMe) on warming. The product was obtained from alcohol in cream-colored needles (0.22 g.), m. p. and mixed m. p. 156-57°.

6-Methoxy-3-(3 : 4-dimethoxybenzyl)-2-propionylcoumarone (VIII, R = COEt) was similarly prepared from ethylmagnesium bromide (ethyl bromide, 1.7 g., magnesium, 0.3 g. and ether, 20 c. c.) and the foregoing nitrile (VIII, R = CN (0.4 g.). as a greenish product, which crystallised from a large volume of alcohol in cream-colored needles, m. p. 171°. (Found : C, 71.0 ; H, 6.2. $C_{21}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 71.2 ; 6.2 per cent). The red solution of the compound in sulphuric acid turns on standing green and finally blue.

6-Methoxy-3-(3 : 4-dimethoxybenzyl)-2-n-butyrylcoumarone (VIII, R = COPr) was also similarly prepared from *n*-propylmagnesium bromide (propyl bromide, 2.0 g., magnesium, 0.3 g. and ether, 25 c. c.) and was crystallised from acetone-alcohol in cream-colored needles, m. p. 148°. (Found : C, 71.6 ; H 6.8. $C_{22}H_{24}O_5$ requires C, 71.8 ; H, 6.5 per cent). The compound dissolves in sulphuric acid with a red coloration which gradually turns green and finally blue.

The *2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* crystallised from nitrobenzene-alcohol in deep red plates, m. p. 160-62°. (Found : N, 9.8. $C_{28}H_{28}O_8N_4$ requires N, 10.2 per cent).

6-Methoxy-3-(3 : 4-dimethoxybenzyl)-2-isobutyrylcoumarone was exactly prepared as its isomer, mentioned above, by employing isopropylmagnesium bromide. The compound crystallised from acetic acid in nearly colorless needles, m. p. 124-25°. (Found : C, 71.5 ; H 6.9. $C_{22}H_{24}O_5$ requires C, 71.8 ; H, 6.5 per cent).

The *oxime* crystallised from aqueous methanol (80%) in colorless needles, m. p. 99-101°. (Found : N, 3.6. $C_{22}H_{25}O_5N$ requires N, 3.7 per cent). The red solution of the substance in sulphuric acid turns slowly green and finally blue.

Cyclisation of (VIII, R = COMe) : Formation of 3 : 8 : 9-Trimethoxy-6-methyl- β -brazan.—The ketone (VIII, R = COMe) (0.15 g.) was heated with glacial phosphoric acid (5 c. c.) in a boiling water-bath for 1 hour. The mixture turned slightly violet and gradually a microcrystalline solid appeared. After heating for 1/2 hour more, the product was worked up as usual. 3 : 8 : 9-Trimethoxy-6-methyl- β -brazan crystallised from pyridine in colorless, elongated hexagonal plates (0.8 g.), m. p. 241-42°. (Found : C, 74.3 ; H, 5.8. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 74.5 ; H, 5.6 per cent). With sulphuric acid the compound develops a beautiful violet-red coloration which gradually turns purple and finally greenish blue.

Cyclisation of (VIII, R = COEt) : Formation of 3 : 8 : 9-Trimethoxy-6-ethyl- β -brazan.—A mixture of the ketone (0.3 g.) was heated and stirred carefully with glacial phosphoric acid (3 c. c.) at 180°-185°. The mixture at first became like a jelly and then a granular precipitate appeared. The product (IV, R = Et) crystallised from pyridine in colorless, shining needles, m. p. 188° (sintering at 184°) ; mixed m. p. with (VIII, R = COEt) was 155°. The analysis was, however, not sharp. (Found : C, 73.9 ; H, 5.9. $C_{21}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 75.0 ; H, 5.9 per cent). With sulphuric acid the compound develops a violet-red coloration which slowly turns purple and then green and finally blue.

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